

A Study of Serum Cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C Levels and Correlation with the Radiological Extent of Disease and Smear Positivity in Pulmonary Tuberculosis

Shivanaik Rayanaikar¹, Ishwara C Havaragi², Niranjan Gangoor³, Arjun Krishnakumar⁴, Abhay Kiran P⁵

^{1,4}Senior Resident, General Medicine, Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences, Belagavi

^{2,3}Senior Resident, General Medicine, S R Patil medical college and research centre, Badagandi

⁵Senior Resident, General Medicine, Chamaraajanagar Institute of Medical Sciences, Chamaraajanagar

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Abhay Kiran P

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Pulmonary tuberculosis is one of the oldest disease affecting the human race since ancient times. However, even with the advent of recent advances in diagnosis and treatment, the morbidity and mortality due to this disease remains high. The primary reason being the increasing incidence of drug resistance and the human immunodeficiency virus infection.

Objective. To study the levels of serum cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C levels in patients with pulmonary Tuberculosis and study the correlation of serum cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C with radiological extent of disease and Sputum positivity.

Methods: 104 patients diagnosed as pulmonary tuberculosis were included in the study after considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria. History was taken, clinical examination was done, relevant investigations were done for all eligible patients. DSP and DRED were calculated and compared with Serum Cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C Levels.

Result: The levels of all the lipids were found to be significantly lower in the advanced tuberculosis group (stage III) as compared with stage II and I. in comparison with DSP, total cholesterol values were 158.6±14.1 (DSP I), 134.9±6.4 (DSP II), 114.5±14.9 (DSP III). HDL-C values were 41.6±5.3 (DSP I), 33.0±4.0 (DSP II), 28.0±5.0 (DSP III). LDL-C values were 100.4±8.7 (DSP I), 87.3±7.5 (DSP II), 77.0±9.0 (DSP III). The difference between the group was statistically significant (p<0.001). In comparison with DRED the values of total cholesterol were 161.0±8.8 (DRED I), 136.8±8.9 (DRED II), 125.8±17.5 (DRED III). HDL-C values were 42.2±4.3 (DRED I), 33.8±4.2 (DRED II), 30.9±6.0 (DRED III). LDL-C values were 101.5±6.7 (DRED I), 89.3±7.3 (DRED II), 82.3±11.1 (DRED III). The difference between the group was statistically significant (p<0.001).

Conclusion: Pre-treatment serum level of TC, HDL-C, LDL-C, have positive correlation with DRED and DSP in PTB patients.

Keywords: TC, HDL-C, LDL-C, DRED and DSP.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is a major public health problem, especially in the developing countries of Asia and Africa. Fuelled by the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) epidemic and the emergence of drug-resistant TB, it poses greater challenges than ever before. [1]

In the late 1800s, pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) was one of the leading causes of ill health and death in most of the world. social and economic development such as improvements in hygiene, incomes, housing and nutrition the numbers of TB cases and deaths started to decline in western Europe, North America and other parts of the industri-

alized world around the turn of the 20th century but Globally and in many countries, however, TB remains a major cause of ill-health and mortality. [2] Tuberculosis is a major public health problem where India accounts for one fifth of the global burden of TB incident cases.

Almost 40 percent of the population in India are infected with TB bacilli. It is second leading cause of death killing 2 million people each year. [3] People with tuberculosis are often malnourished, and malnourished people are also at a risk of developing tuberculosis since their immune systems are weakened. Cholesterol, mainly because of its

involvement in cardiovascular diseases, has received much attention in recent years. However there are increasing evidences that indicate a link between low blood cholesterol levels and number of human diseases including tuberculosis. It is reported that low total cholesterol level promotes the development of TB whereas hypercholesterolemia confers some protection against infection with mycobacterium tuberculosis. [4]

Cell mediated immunity plays a key role in containing the spread of TB, and a slow lymphocytic response is one of the factors responsible for the spread of the infection. Cholesterol plays a distinct role in the maintenance of the cell membrane structure because of its rigid ring. Various studies have shown the importance of cholesterol in the maintenance of cellular immunity and the potential destructive effects of low cholesterol levels on the lymphocytes. Hence it is possible that the serum cholesterol levels could have an impact on the severity of the infection which could possibly be reflected on the chest radiogram. [5]

Chest radiography is one of the main investigations in the workup of patients with TB. Other than grading the sputum smear after acid fast staining for mycobacterium tuberculosis, chest radiography is possibly the only direct investigation available which can grade the severity of the infection. [6]

PTB was diagnosed by chest radiography, clinical presentation and one positive sputum culture finding for mycobacterium tuberculosis. It is considered that the degree of smear positivity (DSP) might be related to the degree of radiological extent of the disease (DRED). [7] The severity on chest radiography has been shown to correlate positively with the severity grade determined by sputum smear examination. [8]

Determination of the Degree of Radiological Extent. DRED was determined after evaluation of chest X-rays independently by two observers and the final decision was by consensus if there were disagreements in interpretation. PTB patients were classified according to their chest X-ray findings as minimal/mild, moderate and advanced.

DRED 1: Minimal lesions included those of mild to moderate density but which did not contain any demonstrable cavitations; they may have involved a small part of one or both lungs.

DRED 2: Moderately severe lesions included mild to moderate density lesions extending up to the total volume of one lung or the equivalent in both lungs;

Dense and confluent lesions limited to one third the volume of one lung; total diameter of cavitation, if present, was <4 cm.

DRED 3: Far advanced lesions were more extensive than moderately severe lesions.

Hence this study is taken up to observe the existence of relationship between pre-treatment serum level of TC, HDL-C, LDL-C, DRED and degree of smear positivity in PTB patients .

Material and Methods: Single Centre and Prospective analytical cross sectional study was conducted among pulmonary tuberculosis patients admitted to KIMS hospital considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Duration of study was two years (01/11/2020 to 30/11/2022). Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethical committee for the present study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age >18 yr of age
- Patients of pulmonary TB diagnosed at DOTS center in our hospital.

Exclusion Criteria:

- HIV infections
- Diabetes mellitus
- Hypertension
- Chronic kidney disease
- Chronic liver disease
- Known primary hyperlipidemias
- Patients on medications (statins, fibrates, aspirin, beta blockers , diuretics) which could alter the lipid profile

Study Methods:

Patients presenting with history, characteristic clinical signs and symptoms of pulmonary tuberculosis are taken into the study. The study was initiated after obtaining informed consent. Relevant history regarding presenting complaints, past history, family history and smoking history was taken. All necessary investigations were done in the patients. The chest x ray and grading of sputum AFB was compared with total cholesterol, HDL, LDL values of the patients

Sample Size:

Based on the 2019 year data in Indian state tb stats the prevalence is $p = 0.676\%$. considering 95% confidence limits and 9% allowable error the sample size is = 104

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software version 17.0. Qualitative variables like age categories, gender, DSP and DRED were presented as frequency and percentages. Bar diagram and pie charts were used for graphical representation of data. Comparison of DSP and DRED with categories of total cholesterol, HDL and LDL was done with chi square test. Comparison of mean levels of total cholesterol, HDL and LDL with DSP and DRED categories was done using one-way ANOVA. Association of number of cavities with DSP grades was assessed with chi square test.

A p value of less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

It was observed that the maximum number of patients were in the group of 21-40 years. It was observed that the maximum number of patients were males.

Results

Table 1: distributions of patients according to DSP

DSP	Number	Percentage
I	56	53.9
II	36	34.6
III	12	11.5
Total	104	100.0

It was observed that the maximum number of patients had DSP grade I. It was observed that the maximum number of patients had DRED grade I.

Table 2: Association of DSP with Total cholesterol

DSP	Total cholesterol (mg/dl)						Total	P-value
	100-130		131-150		>150			
	n	%	n	%	n	%		
I	2	3.6	8	14.3	46	82.1	56	<0.001
II	12	33.3	23	63.9	1	2.8	36	
III	10	83.3	2	16.7	0	0.0	12	
Total	24	23.1	33	31.7	47	45.2	104	

It was observed that as the grade of sputum positivity increased, lower were the total cholesterol levels

Table 3: Association of DSP with HDL cholesterol levels

DSP	HDL cholesterol (mg/dl)						Total	P-value
	20-30		31-40		>40			
	n	%	n	%	n	%		
I	2	3.6	15	26.8	39	69.6	56	<0.001
II	13	36.1	22	61.1	1	2.8	36	
III	10	83.3	2	16.7	0	0.0	12	
Total	25	24.0	39	37.5	40	38.5	104	

It was observed that as the grade of sputum positivity increased, lower were the HDL cholesterol levels

Table 4: Association of DSP with LDL cholesterol levels

DSP	LDL cholesterol (mg/dl)						Total	P-value
	60-80		81-100		>100			
	n	%	n	%	n	%		
I	2	3.6	19	33.9	35	62.5	56	<0.001
II	12	33.3	23	63.9	1	2.8	36	
III	10	83.3	2	16.7	0	0.0	12	
Total	24	23.1	44	42.3	36	34.6	104	

It was observed that as the grade of sputum positivity increased, lower were the LDL cholesterol levels

Table 5: Association of DRED with total cholesterol

DRED	Total cholesterol (mg/dl)						Total	P-value
	100-130		131-150		>150			
	n	%	n	%	n	%		
I	0	0.0	8	16.0	42	84.0	50	<0.001
II	7	29.2	15	62.5	2	8.3	24	
III	17	56.7	10	33.3	3	10.0	30	
Total	24	23.1	33	31.7	47	45.2	104	

It was observed that as the degree of radiological extent of the disease is increased, lower were the total cholesterol levels.

Table 6: Association of DRED With HDL cholesterol

DRED	HDL cholesterol (mg/dl)						Total	P-value
	20-30		31-40		>40			
	n	%	n	%	n	%		
I	0	0.0	14	28.0	36	72.0	50	<0.001
II	7	29.2	16	66.7	1	4.2	24	
III	18	60.0	9	30.0	3	10.0	30	
Total	25	24.0	39	37.5	40	38.5	104	

It was observed that as the degree of radiological extent of the disease is increased, lower were the HDL cholesterol level

Table 7: Association of DRED with LDL cholesterol

DRED	LDL cholesterol (mg/dl)						Total	P-value
	60-80		81-100		>100			
	n	%	N	%	n	%		
I	0	0.0	18	36.0	32	64.0	50	<0.001
II	6	25.0	17	70.8	1	4.2	24	
III	18	60.0	9	30.0	3	10.0	30	
Total	24	23.1	44	42.3	36	34.6	104	

It was observed that as the degree of radiological extent of the disease is increased, lower were the LDL cholesterol levels.

Table 8: Association of DSP with DRED

DSP	DRED						Total	P-value
	Grade II		Grade II		Grade III			
	n	%	N	%	n	%		
I	50	89.3	2	3.6	4	7.1	56	<0.001
II	0	0.0	20	55.6	16	44.4	36	
III	0	0.0	2	16.7	10	83.3	12	
Total	50	48.1	24	23.1	30	28.8	104	

It is observed that as the grade of DSP increased, so the grade of DRED.

Table-9: Association of DSP with Total cholesterol

DSP	Total cholesterol		Minimum	Maximum	P value
	Mean	SD			
I	158.6	14.1	100.0	175.0	
II	134.9	6.4	124.0	153.0	<0.001
III	114.5	14.9	100.0	142.0	

It is observed that the mean difference in between the various grades of sputum positivity was statistically significant.

Table 10: Association of DSP with HDL

DSP	HDL cholesterol		Minimum	Maximum	P value
	Mean	SD			
I	41.6	5.3	20.0	48.0	
II	33.0	4.0	27.0	42.0	<0.001
III	28.0	5.0	20.0	36.0	

It is observed that the mean difference in between the various grades of sputum positivity was statistically significant.

Table 11: Association of DSP with LDL

DSP	LDL cholesterol		Minimum	Maximum	P value
	Mean	SD			
I	100.4	8.7	70.0	110.0	
II	87.3	7.5	78.0	107.0	<0.001
III	77.0	9.0	70.0	94.0	

It is observed that the mean difference in between the various grades of sputum positivity was statistically significant.

Table 12: Association of DRED with total cholesterol

DRED	Total cholesterol		Minimum	Maximum	P value
	Mean	SD			
I	161.0	8.8	144.0	175.0	
II	136.8	8.9	124.0	157.0	<0.001
III	125.8	17.5	100.0	157.0	

It is observed that the mean difference in between the various grades of DRED was statistically significant. It is observed that apical fibrosis was the commonest diagnosis encountered in our study. It is observed that maximum number of patients had a single cavity it is observed that degree of

sputum positivity was higher in patients with multiple cavities

Discussion

The present study is a prospective observational study conducted to study the levels of serumcholes-

terol, HDL-C, LDL-C levels and compare with radiological extent of disease and sputum positivity in patients of newly detected pulmonary tuberculosis.

The most common age group in present study is 21-40 years, whereas in the study done by Sukhesh rao [9] is 31-45 years, in nawas et al [9] is 30 to 50 years. The percentage distribution of male and female population in the present study was 68.3% and 31.7% respectively. The percentage distribution of male and female population in the Sukhesh rao study was 64% and 36 % respectively.

The percentage distribution of male and female population in the Nawaz et al [10] study was 69.7% and 30.3% respectively. The percentage distribution of male and female population in the present study was comparable with Sukhesh rao study and Nawas et al study

In DSP Class 1 the percentage of patients in my study was 53.9 % which was closely comparable to that of Sukhesh rao [9] which has 32.2%.

In DSP Class 2 the percentage of patients in my study was 34.6 % which was closely comparable to that of Sukhesh rao [9] which had 22.5 %.

In DSP Class 3 the percentage of patients in my study was 11.5 % which was not comparable to that of Sukhesh Rao [9] which had 45.1 %.

Overall the percentage distribution of patients in different DSP Class in the present study was closely comparable to that of Sukhesh Rao [9] study

In DRED Class 1 the percentage of patients in present study was 48.1 % which was closely comparable to that of Sukhesh rao [9] which has 50%.

In DRED Class 2 the percentage of patients in present study was 23.1% which was closely comparable to that of Sukhesh Rao [9] which had 22%.

In DRED Class 3 the percentage of patients in present study was 28.9 % which was closely comparable to that of Sukhesh Rao [9] which had 28%.

Overall the percentage distribution of patients in different DRED Class in the present study was closely comparable to that of Sukhesh Rao [9] study.

The distribution of Mean TC, HDL, LDL in different classes of DRED in the present study was comparable with Farzeen et al study.

In another study by Omer deniz et al has also shown a negative and significant correlation between DSP and serum TC levels.

These are compatible with the recent data indicating a cholesterol rich diet might accelerate the sterilization rate of sputum cultures in PTB patients, suggesting that cholesterol should be used as a complementary measure in anti-tuberculous treatment.

[11] In a study by Perez Guzmán et al [11], Adult patients with newly diagnosed pulmonary tuberculosis were hospitalized for 8 weeks and randomly assigned to receive a cholesterol-rich diet (800 mg/d cholesterol [experimental group]) or a normal diet (250 mg/d cholesterol [control group]). All patients received the same four-drug antitubercular regimen (ie, isoniazid, rifampin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol).

Every week, a quantitative sputum culture and laboratory tests were done and respiratory symptoms were recorded. Patients in the experimental group (10 patients) and the control group (11 subjects) were HIV-negative and harbored Mycobacterium tuberculosis that was fully sensitive to antitubercular drugs. Sterilization of the sputum culture was achieved faster in the experimental group, as demonstrated either by the percentage of negative culture findings in week 2 (80%; control group, 9%; $p = 0.0019$) or by the Gehan-Breslow test for Kaplan-Meier curves ($p = 0.0037$). Likewise, the bacillary population decreased faster ($p = 0.0002$) in the experimental group. Respiratory symptoms improved in both groups, but sputum production decreased faster in the experimental group ($p < 0.05$). Laboratory test results did not differ between the groups.

A cholesterol-rich diet accelerated the sterilization rate of sputum cultures in pulmonary tuberculosis patients, suggesting that cholesterol should be used as a complementary measure in antitubercular treatment.

In conclusion, our study has proved that Total cholesterol, HDL, LDL cholesterol levels are lower in patients with severe disease and this has therapeutic implications.

Conclusion

The levels of total cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C were found to progressively decrease in patients with higher degree of sputum positivity. The levels of total cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C were found to progressively decrease in patients with higher degree of radiological extent of the disease. Fibrocavitary lesions was the most common clinical diagnosis followed by Apical fibrosis. Among the fibrocavitary lesions, the higher degree of sputum positivity was found in patients with higher number of cavities.

References

1. Munjal YP, Sharm SK. API Textbook of Medicine, Two Volume Set. JP Medical Ltd; 2012 May 18.
2. Chakaya J, Petersen E, Nantanda R, Mungai BN, Migliori GB, Amanullah F, Lungu P, Ntoumi F, Kumarasamy N, Maeurer M, Zumla A. The WHO Global Tuberculosis 2021 Report—not so good news and turning the tide

- back to End TB. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 2022 Mar 20.
3. Dye C, Scheele S, Dollin P, et al. Global burden of tuberculosis: estimated incidence, prevalence and mortality by country. *JA-MA*. 1999;282:677Y686
 4. Shima Ahmed Hussein Ali and Nuha Eljaili Abubaker. (2017); Assessment of Total Protein, Albumin, Triglyceride and Total Cholesterol among Sudanese Patients with Tuberculosis in Khartoum State. *Int. J. of Adv. Res.* 5 (Sep). 1-6] (ISSN 2320-5407). www.journalijar.com
 5. Nawaz A, Nayak MA, Hameer ST, Kamath A, Mahale A. Correlation between serum lipid fractions and radiological severity in patients with drug-resistant pulmonary tuberculosis: A cross-sectional pilot study. *Indian Journal of Medical Specialities*. 2019 Apr 1; 10(2):99.
 6. Nawaz A, Nayak MA, Hameer ST, Kamath A, Mahale A. Correlation between serum lipid fractions and radiological severity in patients with drug-resistant pulmonary tuberculosis: A cross-sectional pilot study. *Indian Journal of Medical Specialities*. 2019 Apr 1; 10(2):99.
 7. Shima Ahmed Hussein Ali and Nuha Eljaili Abubaker. (2017); Assessment of Total Protein, Albumin, Triglyceride and Total Cholesterol among Sudanese Patients with Tuberculosis in Khartoum State. *Int. J. of Adv. Res.* 5 (Sep). 1-6] (ISSN 2320-5407). www.journalijar.com
 8. Nawaz A, Nayak MA, Hameer ST, Kamath A, Mahale A. Correlation between serum lipid fractions and radiological severity in patients with drug-resistant pulmonary tuberculosis: A cross-sectional pilot study. *Indian Journal of Medical Specialities*. 2019 Apr 1; 10(2):99
 9. Rao S. Serum cholesterol, HDL, LDL levels in pulmonary tuberculosis: A clinico-radiological correlation and implications. *Infectious Diseases in Clinical Practice*. 2009 Mar 1; 17(2):99-101.
 10. Nawaz A, Nayak MA, Hameer ST, Kamath A, Mahale A. Correlation between serum lipid fractions and radiological severity in patients with drug-resistant pulmonary tuberculosis: A cross-sectional pilot study. *Indian Journal of Medical Specialities*. 2019 Apr 1; 10(2):99.
 11. Pérez-Guzmán C, Vargas MH, Quiñonez F, Bazavilvazo N, Aguilar A, Team OS. A cholesterol-rich diet accelerates bacteriologic sterilization in pulmonary tuberculosis. *Chest*. 2005 Feb 1; 127(2):643-51.